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POSTER PRESENTATION

MERCURY EXPOSURE: EVIDENCE FROM A BIOMONITORING STUDY IN WOMEN UNDERGOING IN VITRO FERTILIZATION

Maja Milanović^{1*}, Marko Ilinčić², Jana Pavlović³, Nataša Milošević¹, Artur Bjelica², Nataša Milić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia, *maja.milanovic@mf.uns.ac.rs

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, University Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Branimira Ćosića 37, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

³University of East Sarajevo, Faculty of Medicine Foča, Studentska 5, 73300 Foča, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Having in mind the worldwide observed rising trend of infertility, *in vitro* fertilization (IVF), represents the typically applied assisted reproductive technology for the management of patients with fertility issues. Although the IVF success rate is strongly related to age of women, there is a growing interest in environmental factors that could be related to impaired female reproductive health and success of IVF cycle.

Previous studies suggested that exposure to metalloestrogens might be related to spontaneous abortion, irregular menstrual cycle and even infertility. Hence, the aim of this study was to evaluate the level of exposure to mercury among women undergoing IVF.

In this cross-sectional study 50 women between the ages of 18-45 with preserved ovarian function were included. The recruitment was conducted on voluntary bases at the Special Gynecological Hospital "Genesis", Serbia. Mercury was analyzed in the first morning urine sample after microwave digestion using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry.

Being recognized as an endocrine disruptor, mercury was measured in 60% urine samples (30 out of 50) above the limit of quantification (1.9 µg/L). The obtained average concentration (8.98±11.68 µg/L) in this study was more than two times higher than the 95th percentile urinary value reported in a nation-wide sample of Spanish women (3.99 µg/L). In addition, the average concentration significantly suppressed the urine mercury measurements in pregnant women within National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey in USA (geometric mean 0.25 µg/L). The obtained results indicate that women undergoing IVF in Serbia are long-term exposed to mercury. Based on the literature data the consumption of contaminated fish might be considered as the major source of exposure. The associations of mercury exposure with IVF outcomes require further examination.

Keywords: ICP-MS, environmental pollution, urine, fertility

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